

LGU SCHOLARS' LEVEL OF SATISFACTION TOWARDS THE SCHOLARSHIP PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study elucidates the level of satisfaction among college students with the scholarship provided by a Local Government Unit (LGU) in Misamis Oriental, Philippines which aims to know the perceptions of the scholars with regards to the scholarship's effectiveness, efficiency, and service delivery. This research utilizes a quantitative descriptive research design, a survey questionnaire was distributed to 89 college students who are beneficiaries of the said LGU scholarship program. Findings of the study reveal an overall positive level of satisfaction among the beneficiaries, with a general rating of "Agree" (mean of 4.233). Beneficiaries were particularly satisfied with the accessibility and responsiveness of the scholarship administrators, rating it as "Agree" (mean of 4.224). The study also finds no significant difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped by demographic profiles such as age, sex, or family monthly income. However, despite the high satisfaction, the beneficiaries' assessment of challenges was "Neutral" (mean of 3.017). A notable challenge was the insufficient financial assistance to cover all educational expenses, with a mean score of 3.506, which is close to the "Agree" interpretation. The study concludes that while the program is effective, there are still areas for improvement. It suggests that the LGU needs to review the amount of financial support, considering the ongoing increase of school fees yearly among private schools, and improve communication and support services, as well as administrative processes.

Keywords: *Perception, Satisfaction, Scholarship, Perception, Local Government Unit (LGU), Christ the King College (CKC), Monitoring, Accessibility, Responsiveness, Transparency, Fairness, Financial support, Benefits, Support Services.*

INTRODUCTION

Youth can influence and change any paradigms that are happening in our lifetime. They can be an agent of change, for they are the next generation who would handle and govern our state and nation in a way that they would see fit. Thus, it is very important to let them understand the fundamental and holistic vision on what the system of the government is supposed to be. Even though most of the youth today are not towards the government system and how it works but also most of them are beneficiaries of the services that government offers. Thus, this points to the importance of young people's active participation and responds to change in urban conditions, moreover, understanding themselves as active political actors and mediators rather than passive actors, because of this it produce new city subjectivities and relationships (Lam-Knott & Cheng, 2020).

The schools/university have a great part in this kind of engagement which expresses the importance of academic areas towards the interrelationship between youths and politics. Moreover, it is also part of the changing environment of political actions, create 22 new concept of political participation which started developing and it is expressed that the youth engagement to politics through new kinds of political activities, explains that the youth people today are very diverse from the past generation (Willeck & Mendelberg, 2022).

It is very important to address and understand why most of the youth of today are showing apathy towards government administration and politics thus addressing e inaccessibility of education, financial support, injustice and social exclusions (Kroesen & Moleman, 2025). This compromises the overall satisfaction of the views and perspective of the youth with regards to the benefits and services that he/she can avail. Thus, the need for monitoring and support from the institution, government and groups is very important to avoid excluding those in need of care (Lorber & Dobnik, 2022).

The idea of considering and involving the youth to participate in politics and public governance is an important element in providing a venue for the community to innovate and improve. More experience and insightful analysis of the youth towards their urban experiences could 28 eventually help and assist the evaluation part of innovation and improvement. Considering also the perspective of the youth encourages and invites them to participate in building a better future for the community. On the other hand, discouraging the youth and young people to participate in the government and politics would only lead them to apathy and alienation towards the government and politics. Moreover, taking also into account the Age, Gender/sex, Year and Course of the Students and people to explore unbiased data because these variables varied their perspective depending to their personal experiences and relations to the service that the LGU provides. Thus, understanding the relation between governance and politics towards the

youth and exploring the different sides and perspectives aids the researcher in discovering rich and clear data that would fuel that credibility and purposeful of the research.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents (youth) of the study in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 course;
 - 1.4 year;
 - 1.5 type of scholarship availed; and
 - 1.6 family monthly income?
2. What is the respondents' level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship Program in terms of:
 - 2.1 Accessibility and responsiveness;
 - 2.2 Transparency and Fairness
 - 2.3 Financial Support and Benefits
 - 2.4 Monitoring and Support Services
3. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of satisfaction with Delivery of LGU Scholarship Program when the respondents are grouped according to:
 - 3.1 age;
 - 3.2 sex;
 - 3.3 course;
 - 3.4 year;
 - 3.5 type of scholarship availed; and
 - 3.6 family monthly income?
4. How do respondents assess the benefit of the LGU scholarship program?
5. What is the respondents' assessment of the different challenges when availing the Scholarship program provided by the Local Government Unit (LGU)?
6. Based on the study's findings, what strategic approaches can be recommended to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the Scholarship service provided by the LGU?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used Quantitative research design, specifically descriptive, to explore and determine the performance of a specific Local Government Unit with regards to the scholarship service through analyzing and gathering satisfactory perception, views and experiences coming from the youth particularly the college youth in Christ the King College, Gingoog City. This research would benefit the LGU community in the improvement of their services delivery, for the youth are one of the largest factors in

bringing change through the perception of the youth in a form of evaluation (Moazzem & Shilby, 2020). The researcher applied a quantitative research design in analyzing satisfaction as a form of evaluation on what level and number of college youth is able to receive services with an effective and efficient delivery.

The quantitative descriptive research design delves into understanding the average of the level of satisfaction of the college youth with regards to the service delivery of the LGU community with regards to scholarship programs, which helps describe the satisfaction of the college youth to the scholarship program. Furthermore, this involves data collection such as survey with the use of google forms for easy access and dissemination. This method of gathering data of the level of satisfaction of college youths in Christ the King College can protect privacy of the respondents and at the same time data gathering was much faster and easier.

Research Locale

The research was carried out at the Christ the King College, Gingoog City, Misamis Oriental – Region X. The school (CKC) was an ideal venue for examining the perspectives in determining the satisfactory level of the College Youth Students in exploring the effectiveness and efficiency of the service delivery of Gingoog City's LGU with regards to Scholarship benefits.

Population and Sampling Technique

The study targets the college youths in Christ the King College from 2nd yr to 4th yr college with a 120 population as a means in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery of the LGU community in the area with regards to scholarship benefit. The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to ensure information and qualify the validity of their inputs and views about the research topic. A quantitative approach was used. The researcher gathered data about the demographic profile of the respondents which included age, gender, course, year level, type of scholarship availed and family monthly income. A critical Opinion Scale Questionnaire for the respondents was prepared in determining the satisfactory level of the respondents towards the effectiveness and efficiency of the scholarship service offered by the LGU community.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of this study were (89) college students from 2nd to 4th year college coming from Christ the King College, Gingoog City. (3) participants from Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), (18) participants from 2nd to 4th year college from Bachelor of Secondary Science in Social work (BSSW), (15) Participants from Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA), (16) participants from Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM), (6) Participants from Bachelor of Science in Secondary Education (BSED), (1) participants from Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education (BEED), (20) participants from Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), (10) participants from Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM) and (0) participants from Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT).

The respondents were informed of the purpose of the survey and the ethical consideration that was upheld by the researcher.

Table 1: Respondents of the Study

Year level	Sex	Age
1 st year – 0%	Female – 62.9%	18 to 20 - 70.8%
2 nd year – 42.7%		21 to 23 – 28.1%
3 rd year – 39.3%	Male – 37.1%	24 to 26 - 1.1%
4 th year – 18 %		27 & above – 0%
Course		
BSBA – 3.4%	BSSW – 20.2%	BSCRIM – 19.1%
BSED – 5.6	BEED – 1.1%	BSN – 22.5
BSHM – 11.2%	BSIT – 0%	Others – 0%

They were all given the survey questionnaire based on the following inclusion criteria:

1. Enrolled as a College student in Christ the King College, Gingoog City;
2. Is 18 – 30 years as defined by Republic Act No. 8044;
 - a. 18 – 24 core youth
 - b. 25 – 30 adult youth
3. Have availed the scholarship benefit from the LGU in Gingoog City;
4. Availed the scholarship service under the current administration.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study consisted of a questionnaire through google forms, designed to collect data on the perception of College youths to the effectiveness and efficiency of the LGU's service delivery.

Questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 3 parts, part 1 has 5 sections for Research Question 2, part 2 section for Research Question 4 and part 3 for Research Question 5, corresponding to the research questions.

Part 1: *Scholar's Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship Program*

Section 1 – Accessibility and Responsiveness,

Section 2 – Transparency and Fairness,

Section 3 – Financial Support and Benefits,

Section 4 – Monitoring and Support Service and,
Section 5 – Overall Satisfaction.

Part 2: *Respondent's assessment on Scholarship benefit*

Part 3: *The challenges encountered by the Scholarship beneficiaries*

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

An adopted and modified questionnaire from Customer Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire is validated through a scrutinized process from Dr. Ely Lumbao, Adviser of the researcher, and other (3) validators who were experts in the field of research in the academe namely, Dr. Jaffy Glenn D. Guillena, Mr. Aristeo L. Abecia, MS-Math, Jo Niza B. Mortiz, Ph.Dc, RGC and reliability testing of questionnaire is done by Jayson S. Digamon, EdD, Senior Education Specialist/Research Coordinator of Gingoog City Division.

The instrument was tested with (30) respondents from Bachelor of Science in Accountancy who just graduated. The researcher provided those graduates a google form link where they answered the survey. Results of the test were analyzed and the researcher was issued a certification to proceed with the administration of the research instruments since they were found to be reliable.

Scoring Guidelines and Procedures

In scoring the instruments and interpreting the profile of the respondents, the following scoring guidelines were followed.

For the Level of Satisfaction

Description	Raw Score	Interval
Strongly Disagree	1	1.00 – 1.50
Disagree	2	1.51 – 2.50
Neutral	3	2.51 – 3.50
Agree	4	3.51 – 4.50
Strongly Agree	5	4.51 – 5.00

For Family Monthly Income

Range	Description	Code
P 30, 001 & above	Upper Class	C
P 15, 001 to 30, 000	Middle Class	B
P 15, 000 & Below	Lower Class	A

Data Gathering Procedure

After the pilot testing and validation of the Questionnaire the survey was undergo a procedure in gathering the data.

Step 1 – A letter was sent to the Vice – President for Academic affairs to inform and ask permission for data gathering to those students who are LGU scholars.

Step 2 – The researcher received a letter of approval from the said office.

Step 3 - The participants of the survey were informed face to face or through email or messenger, they were informed about the context of the survey.

Step 4 -The survey questionnaire link from Google forms was disseminated through their emails and messenger with an attached agreed terms of privacy act to protect the privacy of the participants' answers.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools of the data that was used in this study are descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, percentage, and standard deviation to describe the profile of the respondents considering the independent variables set. To determine the perception of the respondents' level of satisfaction to the LGU's service delivery, the researcher employed inferential statistics specifically correlation to find out if there was a relationship between perception score and the other variables.

Quantitative. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as the following:

Weighted Mean. It was used to calculate a balanced average considering altering significance levels assigned to different data points. This method helped synthesize data on perceptions or effectiveness by giving more weight to crucial aspects.

Composite Mean. This method combined multiple measures into a single score, simplifying complex data sets. It was employed to create indications for constructs which offers a clear summary of different data.

Percentage. Percentages were used to present descriptive statistics and findings. They highlighted proportions or changes in data, such as the percentage of agreement on survey statements or adoption rates, making results easy to interpret.

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). This method determined whether there were significant difference between the means of three or more independent groups.

Likert Scale (4P) and Corresponding Remarks. A Likert scale was used to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions. This was also used to determine the respondents' assessment on the quality of scholarship benefit and the challenges

encountered by the scholarship beneficiaries. It typically presented respondents with a statement and asked them to indicate their agreement or disagreement on a scale.

Scale	Interval Range	Interpretation	Description
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree (SD)	This means that the respondent strongly disagrees with the statement.
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree (D)	This means that the respondent disagrees with the statement.
3	2.51 – 3.50	Neutral(N)	This means that the respondent is unsure with the statement.
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree (A)	This means that the respondent agrees with the statement.
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	This means that the respondent strongly agrees with the statement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study collected a data from 89 respondents where data gathered their respective age, sex, course, year level, type of scholarship availed, and family income. The result of the survey determined the demographic and academic profile of the scholarship beneficiaries.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents' Age

Category	Frequency	Percentage
24 - 26 years	0	0
21 - 23 years	26	29.2
18 - 20 years	63	70.8
TOTAL	89	100.0

The table 1 expresses that most of the respondents aged 18-20 years old (70.8%) followed by aged 21 – 23 years old (29.2%). There were no respondents above 23 years old. This means that majority of the scholarship beneficiaries belong to the younger generation which suggests early and timely admission to higher education (Nass, 2025).

Table 2
Distribution of Respondents' Sex

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Female	56	62.9
Male	33	37.1
TOTAL	89	100.0

In table 2, it shows that female respondents comprised 62.9% of the total respondents and the male respondents is composed of 37.1%. This explains that female respondents are more epitomized among scholarship beneficiaries thus, reflects higher participation among students in the institution studied which means that females show more interest to finish college and so applied and availed of scholarship benefits. Moreover, it implies that statistically female students go to school and are able to avail scholarships than males. A study of Nass in 2025, “The 2025 Comprehensive College Scholarship Statistics Report” also has the same findings. In the study, Nass found out that most women are more likely into applying scholarship assistance compared to men.

Table 3
Distribution of Respondents’ Course

Category	Frequency	Percentage
BSBA	3	3.4
BSSW	18	20.2
BSA	15	16.9
BSCRIM	16	18.0
BSED	6	6.7
BEED	1	1.1
BSN	20	22.5
BSHM	10	11.2
BSIT	0	0
Others	0	0
TOTAL	89	100.0

Based on Table 3, the respondents were enrolled in varied programs. The largest program population enrolled is Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) which is 22.5%, followed by Bachelor of Science in Social Work (BSSW), 20.2%, then Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM), 18% and lastly, Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) 16.9%. On the other hand, programs such as Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM) had only 11.2%, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) 3.4%, Bachelor of Science in Secondary Education (BSED), 6.7% and Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education (BEED), 1.1% were represented smallest.

This shows that students were more interested in enrolling in healthcare related programs compared to pre-teacher service programs. Students and parents recognize the increasing demands of health care service employability after college graduation. Results support the study of American Association of Colleges of Nursing (2022) about the increase of hiring of Health care professionals most especially on nursing care and after they graduate in their baccalaureate degree most of them were automatically hired by hospitals and clinics in local or abroad.

Table 4
Distribution of Respondents' Year Level

Category	Frequency	Percentage
4 th year	15	16.9
3 rd year	35	39.3
2 nd Year	39	43.8
1 st Year	0	0
TOTAL	89	100.0

Table 4 indicates that majority of the respondents/beneficiaries were between 2nd year which is 43.8% and 3rd year which is 39.3% availed the scholarship. Only 16.9% were 4th year students. The 1st year students were not included since they did not have that much experience yet in the program. Most of the CKC students who have availed the scholarship program are from the 2nd year level.

Table 5
Distribution of Respondents' Types of Scholarship Availed

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Full Scholar	36	40.4
Half Scholar	53	59.6
TOTAL	89	100.0

Table 5 indicates that 59.6% of respondents were half scholars, and only 40.4% were full scholars. The data explains that majority of the respondents avail only half-scholarship. This calls for larger budget allocation in the LGU to support wider population. This implies that majority of the Full scholars were able to pass the criteria and qualified as full scholars because aside from academic excellence and privileges, family income is one of the important criteria to qualify a student to avail a full scholarship (Berlanga & Corti, 2025).

Table 6
Distribution of Respondents' Family Monthly Income

Category	Frequency	Percentage
30,001 & above	0	0
15,001 to 30,000	11	12.4
15,000 & below	78	87.6
TOTAL	89	100.0

Table 6 reveals that majority of the respondents comprising 87.6% belong to a family income of ₱15,000 and below. Only 12.4% had income between ₱15,001–₱30,000. Moreover, there were no respondents with the family income above ₱30,000. This explains that scholarship programs are largely serving students from low-income

families, lining with the criteria for financial aid. The study on “Impact of scholarships on university academic performance: a comparative analysis of students with and without scholarships” by Berlanga & Corti, 2025 also supports this notion.

This category shows the overall level of satisfaction of scholarship recipients with the service delivery of the LGU scholarship program, focusing on the five key domains: Accessibility and Responsiveness, Transparency and Fairness, Financial Support and Benefits, Monitoring and Support Services, and overall Satisfaction. The answers were measured using a 5-points Likert scale, the scores from 3.51 – 4.50 were interpreted as “Agree”, expresses a positive evaluation.

Table 7
Distribution of Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship (Accessibility and Responsiveness)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	The scholarship in charge is approachable and accessible for inquiries.	4.315	1.0933	Agree
2	I receive timely responses to my inquiries and concerns.	4.135	1.1200	Agree
3	Scholarship guidelines and procedures are clearly communicated.	4.270	1.1156	Agree
4	Announcements regarding scholarship status and requirements are posted promptly.	4.213	1.1528	Agree
	Overall	4.224	1.0471	Agree

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51–2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

Table 7 revealed that the respondents expressed a positive level of satisfaction towards the accessibility and responsiveness of the scholarship in-charge. The highest mean (M= 4.315) is documented in indicator, “*The scholarship in charge is approachable and accessible for inquiries*” followed by M = 4.270 for indicator, “*Scholarship guidelines and procedures are clearly communicated*”. The overall mean is 4.224 which shows the agreeable level of satisfaction by the scholars/beneficiaries. Therefore, the result proves that the LGU office is approachable and timely in responding to scholars’ inquiries. This implies that frequent and timely communication greatly improves and affects the overall effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery. This notion is supported by the study of Flores and Asuncion, 2020 during pandemic time entitled “*Toward an improved risk/crisis communication in this time of COVID-19 pandemic: a baseline study for Philippine local government units.*” Result of the study reveals that constant open communication greatly contributes to the success of projects, programs, and activities.

Table 8
Distribution of Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship (Transparency and Fairness)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	The selection process for the scholarship is transparent.	4.022	1.1076	Agree
2	The criteria for evaluating scholars are clearly explained to me.	4.022	1.1964	Agree
3	The disbursement of scholarship benefits is handled fairly.	4.022	1.2521	Agree
4	Complaints and appeals are addressed fairly and impartially.	4.011	1.2200	Agree
	Overall	4.009	1.0731	Agree

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51–2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

Table 8 indicates that the respondents agreed towards the transparency and fairness of the scholarship process including the transparency of the selection process, clarifying the evaluation criteria, fairness in distribution, and management of complaints with the mean of 4.022, The overall mean of 4.009 affirms a generally positive perception, though to some extent lower than the accessibility area, expressing a room for improvement in communication and procedural clarity. This implies that creating a venue for fairness, accountability and transparency in the distribution of scholarships and scholarship beneficiaries, effectively, contributes to a more equitable and effective system of educational support (Fajardo, et al., 2024).

Table 9
Distribution of Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship (Financial Support and Benefit)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	I receive my financial support on time.	3.809	1.1568	Agree
2	The amount of financial support is sufficient for my academic needs.	3.618	1.2659	Agree
3	The scholarship covers essential academic expenses (e.g., tuition, books).	3.685	1.2395	Agree
4	I am thankful with the overall financial assistance provided.	4.292	1.1600	Agree
	Overall	3.838	1.0332	Agree

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51–2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

As shown in table 9, this area had the lowest satisfactory level having a mean of 3.838 though it still falls within the “Agree” level. Respondents were least satisfied with the adequacy of financial support for academic needs, which is 3.618 and the coverage of essential expenses is 3.685. However, they expressed a satisfactory result from the support they received, which is 4.292, expressing gratefulness. Scholars find financial aid not enough to fully meet their academic needs. Even though the result does not provide

enough aid that would cover their academic needs, it also implies that it still provides an advantage to the rest of the students because they can focus on studying and finishing their studies. Abing, et al. in 2024 has same findings in her study, "Impact & Effectiveness of ASA Philippines Foundation Scholarship Program on Clients' Children." Any scholarship assistance really lessens students' financial stress.

Table 10
Distribution of Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship (Monitoring and Support Services)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	The scholarship in charge monitors scholars' academic performance regularly.	4.124	1.1263	Agree
2	Academic and emotional support (like counseling, guidance) is available when needed.	3.854	1.1536	Agree
3	The office in-charge is approachable whenever I meet them for any scholarship concern.	4.202	1.1695	Agree
4	The in-charge provides guidance for scholars' development and well-being.	4.112	1.1326	Agree
	Overall	4.062	1.0683	Agree

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51–2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

In Table 10, the respondents agreed that LGU scholarship in-charge provides enough academic monitoring and support, with an average mean of 4.062. Scholars recognized the approachability of the scholarship in-charge with a mean of 4.202 and the availability of guidance for their well-being with a mean of 4.112. However, other services like counseling got the mean of 3.8534, which is a lower rating. But generally, the results show that in the monitoring areas, it is mostly in place and well provided. Well monitored and supported beneficiaries are more likely to excel and respond satisfactorily to the given scholarship. This notion is consistent with the study of Berlanga & Corti, 2024 which is about "Impact of scholarships on university academic performance: a comparative analysis of students with and without scholarships". Results show that indeed, scholars that are well monitored and supported are likely to excel and respond satisfactorily to the scholarship.

Table 11
Distribution of Respondents' Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship (Overall Satisfaction)

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	I am satisfied with the overall service delivery of the scholarship program.	4.124	1.1853	Agree
2	I feel valued and supported as a scholar of LGU Gingoog.	4.191	1.1954	Agree
3	I would recommend this scholarship program to other students.	4.315	1.1735	Agree

4	The scholarship program has helped me succeed in my academic journey.	4.303	1.1813	Agree
	Overall	4.233	1.1418	Agree
Legend:	4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree	3.51 – 4.50 Agree	2.51-3.50 Neutral	
	1.51–2.50 Disagree	1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree		

In table 11, it presents the highest general evaluation with an overall satisfactory mean of 4.233. The respondents strongly agreed with statement 3, “*I would recommend this scholarship program to other students*” with a mean of 4.315 and statement 4, “*The scholarship program has helped me succeed academically*” with a mean of 4.303. The findings indicate that the scholarship program by the LGU is appreciated, perceived as aiding and contributed positively to the academic achievements of the beneficiaries. A study about “Impact of scholarships on student’s academic achievement in Punjab, Pakistan” by Umm e Habiba and Madiha Liaqat also supports this result. Beneficiaries are really grateful for any financial aid given and afforded to them whether big or small. Any academic support is appreciated because it helps lessen academic stress.

Table 12
Difference in Respondents’ Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship When Grouped According to Their Demographic Profile

Respondents’ Characteristics	Level of Satisfaction (Phonemic Awareness)		Interpretation
	F- value	P- value	
Age	.391	.533	Not Significant
Sex	.842	.361	Not Significant
Course	.585	.767	Not Significant
Year	.212	.809	Not Significant
Type of Scholarship Availed	1.917	.170	Not Significant
family monthly income	.187	.667	Not Significant

Table 12 presents the "Difference in Respondents’ Level of Satisfaction with Service Delivery of LGU Scholarship When Grouped According to Their Demographic Profile." Results indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction among respondents when grouped by various characteristics. Particularly, the following characteristics showed no significant relationship with the level of satisfaction. All P-values are greater than 0.05, which will lead to the interpretation that none of these respondent characteristics are significant factors influencing their level of satisfaction with the service delivery of the LGU scholarship. Therefore, it further implies that the demographic profile of the scholars do not matter in their level of satisfaction. However, according to Yelca, et al., 2022, in their study entitled “Citizens’ assessment on programs for education of the local government unit of Banga, Aklan”. It contradicts to the result because it has been found out in their study that the financial and profile of the scholar when grouped according to age, sex, course, year level, type of scholarship availed and family monthly income, affects and influence the level of satisfaction.

Table 13
Respondent's assessment on Scholarship benefit

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	The scholarship benefit provided adequate financial support to meet my educational needs.	3.876	1.2506	Agree
2	The scholarship program was well organized and easy to understand.	4.112	1.1425	Agree
3	The scholarship benefit helped improve my academic performance.	4.112	1.1817	Agree
4	I am satisfied with the communication and support provided by the scholarship administrators.	4.169	1.1000	Agree
5	The scholarship benefit included valuable additional resources (e.g., mentoring, workshops).	3.787	1.2198	Agree
6	Receiving the scholarship reduced my financial stress significantly.	4.067	1.2135	Agree
7	The criteria for awarding the scholarship were clear and fair.	4.045	1.1571	Agree
8	The scholarship benefits positively impacted my overall college experience.	4.157	1.1271	Agree
9	The scholarship program provided timely updates and information.	4.146	1.1337	Agree
10	I felt pressure to maintain a high academic performance to keep the scholarship.	3.787	1.1528	Agree
Overall		4.026	1.0366	Agree

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51–2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

Table 13 presents the overall mean satisfaction is 4.026 which fall under “Agree”. Most of the indicators reveal that scholarship beneficiaries rated “Agree” in most of the aspects of the scholarship in terms of monitoring and support services. This implies that administrators are the key factors in reaching a satisfactory connection between the beneficiary and the guarantor. This conforms to the study of Michel (2025) on “Unraveling how intermediary-beneficiary interaction shapes policy implementation. According to the intermediary and beneficiary relationship in the said study, the intermediary acts as the guarantor that ensures the proper delivery of the services provided and obligations of the guarantee.

Table 14
The Challenges encountered by the Scholarship beneficiaries

No.	Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
1	The financial assistance provided by the LGU scholarship was insufficient to cover my educational expenses.	3.506	1.2624	Neutral
2	I experienced delays in the release of scholarship funds.	3.315	1.2667	Neutral

3	The process of applying for the scholarship was not straightforward and uneasy to understand.	3.000	1.3568	Neutral
4	I encountered difficulties in submitting the required documents for scholarship application or renewal.	2.933	1.4601	Neutral
5	The scholarship renewal process required too many documents and was time-consuming.	2.966	1.4178	Neutral
6	Communication from the LGU regarding scholarship updates and requirements was unclear and untimely.	2.764	1.4618	Neutral
7	I had to wait in long queues or face delays when renewing my scholarship.	3.011	1.3609	Neutral
8	I faced challenges balancing part-time work and academic responsibilities due to financial constraints.	2.989	1.3271	Neutral
9	Some professors were strict or unsupportive, adding to my challenges as a scholarship beneficiary.	2.966	1.4178	Neutral
10	I experienced difficulties understanding the criteria and processes for scholarship eligibility and retention.	2.719	1.4221	Neutral
Overall		3.017	1.1795	Neutral

Legend: 4.51- 5.00 Strongly Agree 3.51 – 4.50 Agree 2.51-3.50 Neutral
1.51-2.50 Disagree 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree

Table 14, The Challenges encountered by the scholarship beneficiaries, shows a general neutral perspective among respondents in terms of challenges faced with the LGU scholarship's service delivery. The overall mean is 3.017 with a standard deviation of 1.1795, which falls within the "Neutral" interpretation (2.51-3.50).

While most aspects are rated as "Neutral," some lean towards slight disagreement or agreement within that range. Particularly, the highest mean, 3.506, reveals that respondents are close to "Agree" with the statement: "The financial assistance provided by the LGU scholarship was insufficient to cover my educational expenses". Respondents are "Neutral" regarding "I experienced delays in the release of scholarship funds" (mean = 3.315). On the indicator, "The process of applying for the scholarship was not straightforward and uneasy to understand," it has a mean of 3.000, which belongs within "Neutral". Likewise, on indicator, "I had to wait in long queues or face delays when renewing my scholarship," it has a mean of 3.011, which is interpreted as "Neutral".

Other indicators such as "I encountered difficulties in submitting the required documents for scholarship application or renewal" (mean = 2.933), "The scholarship renewal process required too many documents and was time-consuming" (mean = 2.966), "I faced challenges balancing part-time work and academic responsibilities due to financial constraints" (mean = 2.989), and "Some professors were strict or unsupportive, adding to my challenges as a scholarship beneficiary" (mean = 2.966) are also interpreted as "Neutral".

The indicator, "I experienced difficulties understanding the criteria and processes for scholarship eligibility and retention," got a lowest mean of 2.719 which is still within the "Neutral" range. Also, "Communication from the LGU regarding scholarship updates

and requirements was unclear and untimely" also has a relatively low mean of 2.764, interpreted as "Neutral".

This means that beneficiaries faced minimal challenges and hardship which implies that the scholarship program provided by the LGU is efficient and effective as well. The services provided do make student life less difficult. The effectiveness of this program and service provided depends on the design and implementation of the policies accompanying the beneficiaries and aiding throughout the service term, moreover, responds to their specific needs. A study of Berlanga & Corti in 2025 on "Impact of scholarships on university academic performance: a comparative analysis of students with and without scholarships" also points out that when program effectiveness largely is dependent on its design and implementation policies to respond to the targeted needs to be addressed.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. Demographic profile:

- 1.1 Age category: According to the result, the profile of the respondents in terms of age are commonly between 18 – 20 years old and only few who availed the scholarship who were between 21 – 23 years old. Thus, it explains that scholars ages range only between 18 - 23 years old.
- 1.2 Sex: In the result, majority of the scholars who availed the scholarship program were females and only 37.1% are males who availed the scholarship.
- 1.3 Course: Among the 8 courses of students who availed the scholarship program in the LGU community, majority of the scholars were coming from nursing program.
- 1.4 Year Level: The result presented that among the 2nd to 4th years students in CKC only 3rd year and 2nd year were the highest respondents which expressed that those middle year level still able to qualify the scholarship and maintain their academic excellence.
- 1.5 Type of Scholarship: The result expressed that those who were able to benefit from the scholarship program from the LGU community were able to avail only half scholar due to qualifications and academic excellence.
- 1.6 Family monthly income: Majority of the scholars were coming from families with "15 000 & below" monthly income. Thus, this is the major qualifications to avail the scholarship program.

2. Level of satisfaction with service delivery of LGU scholarship in terms of:

- 2.1 Transparency and Fairness: The positive response given by the respondents were driven by the transparency and fairness provided by the scholarship in-charge. This determining factor of transparency and fairness pushes the scholars to continue to pursue the scholarship, at

the same time, they are able to see a level ground and a chance to avail the scholarship.

2.2 Financial Support and Benefit: Most of the respondent's response were positive however, majority explains that it was not enough to suffice their full financial necessity. On the other hand, even though it was not enough they cannot deny that it really helps and aids their financial struggles in life specially in their academics.

2.3 Monitoring and Support Services: It is always a good factor for a scholar's positive response the monitoring services provided by the scholarship program. Scholarship program's intention does not end after they distributed, they financial aid but also after they gave the aid because in that way they are able to determine the effectiveness of the program. Thus, the scholars were able to see visibly the monitoring and support services that the program provides which leads to a positive response from them.

2.4 Overall Satisfaction: For the overall satisfaction, Beneficiaries are really grateful for any financial aid given and afforded to them whether big or small. Any academic support is appreciated because it helps lessen academic stress.

3. Level of Satisfaction when grouped according to their profile: When grouped according to age, sex, course, year level, type of scholarship availed and monthly family income, there are no influence on the level of satisfaction in terms of service delivery of the scholarship program.
4. Respondents' assessment on Scholarship Benefit: According to the data, the respondents provided a "Agree" response to the scholarship benefit. Thus, explaining the effectiveness of the scholarship program and in-charge of the scholars, in helping and aiding their studies and academic success.
5. The challenges encountered by the Scholarship beneficiaries: In this area, the data provided a rich result since there are a lot of conclusions that we can make but the most recommended is that the scholarship program even though it is effective and efficient. It also leaves a room for improvement since there are other areas and aspects that the respondents wish to be addressed but it does not largely affect the satisfactory perception of the scholarship program.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. The study found out that. While beneficiaries were generally satisfied, the financial assistance was insufficient to cover all their educational expenses. A scholarship fund needs to be augmented fundamentally to address the increasing costs of education and to ensure that more deserving students, especially those from low-income families can access higher education without financial challenges. LGU should consider reviewing and possibly increasing the amount of financial support to better meet the academic needs of the scholars. Additional budget for this

program be augmented for sustainability. Increasing the scholarship fund shall assist with the financial gaps that students encounter such as tuition, books, and living expenses, reducing their need to work excessively during studies and lessening student loan problems.

2. The study found out that only few students in private school were able to avail the scholarship programs. This might due to misinformation and unclear posting of such scholarship programs, resulting to misinformation about the qualifications to avail the scholarship program and many others. Disseminating scholarship information extensively allows possible applicants, including deserving students, be aware of opportunities, eligibility criteria, deadlines, and application processes. More students from different backgrounds, including those with inadequate resources, can apply and avail the program that supports social equity in education by providing equal access to information.
3. The study allows the academic community especially the teachers, to explain to those students to give value on their studies by doing their best in school. Advise students that the scholarship program must not be taken for granted for this is a great opportunity they have enjoyed and that they are lucky not burdened with school fees for many had not availed of this financial assistance due to the limited number of scholarship slots.
4. Considering that monitoring and support service provided is a good factor for a scholar's positive response in the scholarship program, there is a need to maintain and improve the monitoring system of the program that allows timely identification of academic difficulties, enabling immediate intervention or counseling that supports scholars maintain or improve their grades. Furthermore, support services such as peer engagement provide scholars with a sense of belonging-ness, therefore, reducing stress and increasing their confidence.
5. Based on respondents' assessment on scholarship benefit, scholarship in-charge are key factors in reaching a satisfactory connection between the beneficiary and the guarantor. When the scholarship in-charge does his/her duties effectively, he builds trust and confidence among beneficiaries, assuring students that the sponsor is reliable and responsive to their needs. This positive relationship improves beneficiaries' overall satisfaction with the program and enhances the perceived value of the scholarship beyond just financial aid. On the contrary, any lack of engagement by the scholarship in-charge may create gaps in service, or dissatisfaction, therefore, waning the bond between beneficiaries and guarantors and possibly undermining the program's accomplishment. With this, investing in training, and empowering the scholarship in-charge is essential to foster transparency, responsiveness, and a strong bond which increases the scholarship's impact on students' academic and personal development.
6. The researcher wishes to inspire future researchers to conduct a similar study looking into the other aspects of the scholarship programs of other LGUs in the country to better improve their services and possibly help in their agenda of poverty reduction by 2030.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher guaranteed the integrity of the research undertaking by strictly following ethical and professional standards provided by the Graduate School. Privacy and dignity of participants were a priority. The conduct of the research was within the framework of ethical considerations: consent, confidentiality, and respect for the participants were followed. The participants' answers were regarded with full confidentiality and privacy by ensuring them to conceal the names and personal details of the participants in the data analysis.

In conducting this study, the following ethical guidelines were strictly adhered to:

Informed Consent. The School's Vice President for Academic Affairs (VPAA) was informed and given a letter of permission to conduct a survey questionnaire for the research. Moreover, the participants in the survey were informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Before data collection.

Confidentiality. Strict confidentiality was employed to all gathered data. Participants' identities were strictly obscured, and data was gathered securely. The data was available only to the researcher.

Voluntary Participation. Participation in the study was not forceful and is completely voluntary. Participants choose whether to participate or not in the study in their own accord.

Minimization of Harm. Efforts were made to reduce any potential harm to participants during data gathering and spreading of findings.

Respect for Participants. The researcher followed the ethical and professional standards provided by the school to uphold all participants' dignity, rights, and privacy throughout the research process.

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